

A legal perspective on language, oppression and naming practices in South Africa

Cindy Devani Delomoney¹, Zeanette Naidu²

Abstract

The progressive nature of the South African constitution in solidifying and safeguarding women’s rights, including the right to dignity and equality, is highly regarded. The formulation of these realities has been undermined by the legacy of apartheid and colonialism, which have complicated the evolution of legislation and language in South Africa. Language and the legal system are inextricably linked, and discriminatory practices against women are still prevalent today. The objective of the article is to demonstrate the overt and covert oppression of African women by language and law. It will examine the stereotypical roles that women frequently assume in society (wife, mother, and daughter) in relation to the laws that govern naming practices. Our discussion will consider the Birth and Death Registrations Act 51 of 1992, the Children’s Act 38 of 2005, and the Civil Union Act 17 of 2006 in terms of their naming practices and their consequences for women. We contend that the law favours men and instils prejudice against women, resulting in inequality between men and women and the denial of women’s access to justice due to discrimination against female subjects in naming conventions.

Keywords

legislation in South Africa, women’s inequality, women’s surnames

¹ Mangosuthu University of Technology, Department of Accounting & Law, South Africa, E-mail: delomoney.devani@mut.ac.za, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7816-5708>

² Varsity College, Department of Law, South Africa, E-mail: znaidu@varsitycollege.co.za, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-5104-1281>

Introduction

Globally, the South African constitution is acknowledged for its progressive nature. It effectively solidifies and safeguards the rights of women. In addition to ensuring the right to dignity and equality, it affords women several additional constitutional protections. However, the formulation of legislation and the development of language in South Africa has been somewhat complicated. The evolution of these two realities have been undermined by the relationship between apartheid and colonialism (West & Zimmerman, 2009). These discriminatory practises against women are still evident today. One aspect of that is the inextricable relationship between language use and the legal system. Language serves as the medium for drafting policies, legislation and the verbal communication used in court. Law also reflects social structures and more importantly, it perpetuates the existing differences in power. The presence of eleven official languages, four ethnic categories, and diverse cultures within this nation further complicates matters the relationship between language and the law in the country (Constitution 1996).

Section 9(3) of the 1996 Constitution states that neither the state nor any person can unfairly discriminate against someone, either directly or indirectly. It is against the law to discriminate against anyone on various grounds particularly one should not be prejudiced based on their race, sexual orientation or gender. This formulation should not allow for patriarchal practises that exploit and discriminate against women. The purpose of this analysis is, nevertheless, to explore the overt and covert ways in which language and law function together to oppress women in respect of naming practises. The discussion will draw on the legal framework and relevant case law highlighting the different roles that women play in society. We shall point out the deep-rooted psychological implications for women's sense of self. Our aim is to reveal that the gender-biased prejudice found in naming conventions stems from the terminology utilised by government and legal systems, which ultimately perpetuate women's insubordination (Bonthys, 2001).

Literature Review

Studies reveal that African societies are organised in a patriarchal manner. This refers to the social structure and system of beliefs that establish and maintain the superiority of males over females and children (Resane, 2023). Human rights in South Africa is governed by constitutional imperatives as well as by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The 1996 Constitution (hereafter referred to as the Constitution) symbolises our collective national identity and serves as a source of inspiration for its people. Section (9)3 of the Constitution recognises individual identity rights irrespective of race, colour, gender, sexual orientation, language, culture and religion. Despite the entrenchment of these rights, literature indicates that the transference of rights from paper to practice has been fraught with tensions and poses challenges particularly for women (Tshipani, 2021; Bertucci et al, 2021).

There is also a strong international policy framework on the importance of consensual marriages that the Constitution observes. According to Article 16(1) of the 1948 Universal

Declaration of Human Rights, men and women aged 18 and over have the right to marry and start a family. They are entitled to equal privileges throughout and after marriage. Article 16(2) of the Universal Declaration states that marriage requires the free and full consent of the individuals involved. In addition to the Universal Declaration, the 1964 Convention on Permission to Marriage states that no marriage can be lawfully entered into without the full and voluntary consent of both parties (Article 1). According to Article 16 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), State Parties must eliminate discrimination against women in marriage and family relations, a position that has its foundation on the fundamentally liberal and democratic positions of the country's Constitution. This includes ensuring equal rights for men and women to enter marriage, choose a spouse, and enter marriage only with consent. The purpose of these policies is to ensure that ratifying countries co-operate and implement comprehensive, coherent laws to deal with key developmental issue of protecting and enhancing women's rights.

Several theorists indicate that British colonialism and the apartheid rule raped and pillaged land and people which resulted in misplaced or distorted identity formation for men and women (Machaba, 2004; Resane 2023). In fact, we can go as far as stating that colonialism has had significant generational impact on the development of South African people's sense of identities and values of themselves. In such a process democracy, unity, clear and accepted ideology must be based on de-colonial perspectives (Wa Thiong'o, 1993). The African liberation struggles which led to South Africa's democracy in 1994 should be the stairway to decolonial epistemic perspectives that provide the facilitation in a process leading to democratic decolonisation (Wa Thiong'o, 1993).

This unfavourable situation works as a double-edged sword for African women due to the intersectional oppressional factors they experience. British colonialism defined the South African women in the most unfavourable manner, starting as early as the 18th century with narratives of Saartjie Baartman (Crais and Scully, 2021). Baartman was referred to as the “Hottentot Venus,” which serves as an important reminder of how colonial powers exploited and objectified the bodies of African women, distorting and undermining their identities.

One of the key legacies of colonialism in South Africa in the legal field is the common-law, which is a combination of Roman Dutch Law and English Law. Both these inherited systems of law utilized their systems and legal processes to oppress and marginalise women. Regarding the specific practices of naming there is no “cultural pureness or authenticity” in the use of surnames in South Africa (Nduna, 2014, p.31). Whilst it is difficult to state exactly when the use of surnames started in Africa, there are various global views on where surnames originated (Madubuike, 1976, p.45). Whether they have their roots in Italy and France or from Sanskrit the common factor is that they were established outside South Africa (Machaba, 2004, p.139). Further, colonisers without doubt also had a role to play with surname usage in Africa.

In South Africa, before the colonial rule, indigenous people did not use surnames, but they had clan names which identified them in terms of the group they belonged to (Machaba, 2004, p.139). In addition, indigenous names also have a significant social aspect to them.

They are derived from various aspects of everyday life, family dynamics, parent-child relationships, family circumstances, the influence of God during birth, and the clan's identity (Achemfuor, 2018, p.5). The social element too permeates African society in the recognition of the family, God and the clan to which they belong too. It also serves as a foundation on which these long-standing beliefs of the designated role that each member plays within that society in upholding and reinforcing these structures which have been often called unjust and oppressive particularly towards females and female children. There was a myriad of reasons like colonial administration, bureaucracy and the keeping of registers that compelled colonisers to introduce surnames amongst the indigenous people (Machaba, 2004, p.141). The introduction of surnames was a means of colonialist oppression in the surveillance of indigenous people.

South African women's rights and their roles have only been given serious recognition over the last three or four decades. Previously the history of women's political organization, their struggle for freedom from apartheid, oppression, community rights, especially with regards to gender equality was largely ignored in history as well as within the institutions of teaching and learning. Books and knowledge taught in schools and universities was based on white political development while the majority of the history of the other racial groups survived through their social interactions which ultimately led to the liberation struggles of the oppressed (Wa Thiong'o, 1993). On the other side the achievements of white men were reflected through their military exploits and leadership capabilities whilst the country's women were left completely left out of South African history (RSA History Online, 2024).

36

There are no direct laws or policies specifically dealing with surnames and naming practices nor are their legal precedents in South Africa. Nevertheless, the Births and Deaths Registration Act of 1992 and the Recognition of the Customary Marriages Act of 1998 that involve regulations of naming. South Africa historically is a multi-racial country including multiple cultures which can be broken down from the biggest being Black South Africans, Coloureds: a mixed racial group, White South Africans to the smallest being Indian South Africans (South African Government, 2024)

The reality of the situation is that the South Africa's Constitution led to a new era for all previously disadvantaged groups, particularly women who were also oppressed by men of their own race under apartheid. It has been believed that the new government meant the end of apartheid's institutionalised racism. The debates on this still exist, however research indicates that there is extremely limited scholarship on how gender, race and equality interlock in the lives of African women. This reality means that racism persists alongside sexism and results in unequal outcomes for African women. The lack of political will to deal with structures and cultures of an oppressive society is a reality. The contribution of this paper lies in re-igniting the debates concerning the place of women in post-apartheid South Africa (Ndinda and Ndlovu, 2022).

One such practise is *ukuthwala* (forced marriages of a minor girl to an older man) a traditional African practice that is particularly evident among the Ngunis in South Africa (Mkhize and Vilakazi, 2021). It not only perpetuates a direct violation of the women's rights to individual autonomy and bodily integrity, but also promotes patriarchal control of

female sexuality, thereby upholding that gendered violence of girls as acceptable. Chelete Monyane (2013, p.66) points out that *ukuthwala* is a form of coerced marriage that “exposes women and children to sexual and domestic violence.” In terms of *ukuthwala* a girl child can be “selected” as a bride and married against her will where despite customary law requiring consent as a pre-requisite to marriage and establishing the age of consent to be 18 years of age she will be forced into marriage and additionally coerced to adopt her alleged husband’s surname.

From an African perspective, procreation is gendered as well. The birth of female children is viewed as a means of wealth and the birth of sons is a sign of prosperity (Resane, 2023). The weight attached to gender not only points to inequality and simultaneously denies women the right to ownership and prosperity as prosperity itself is synonymous with economic growth and ownership. This sense of ownership against the background of patriarchy extends to naming conventions not restricted to the title of mother, daughter, or wife but to adopting the surnames of fathers and husband’s which speaks to the transition and passing on of ownership. Consequently, a woman’s identity becomes submerged under that of her father and then husband and she is not her own person with her own perspectives (Kiesling, 2019). Historically, the law and the legal system has played a crucial role in perpetuating the oppression of women in this regard making law into a strategically used tool of men’s dominance over women, producing and upholding the socio-political structures of patriarchy and male superiority.

English, the language of the British colonisers in South Africa has been embraced and acknowledged by a significant number of South Africans in the diaspora and South Africa to some extent (Lafon, 2006; Atanga et al, 2012). In South Africa despite there being eleven official languages recognised in the Constitution, English continues to be the primary language of communication and/or lingua franca in the country. Additionally, the policies of governance and legislation are also written in English. Given the structural inequalities across the various racial and cultural groups, especially in rural areas, women who are more likely not to speak English are alienated from the language of the law should they seek legal protection (Ndinda and Ndlovu, 2022). The colonial legacy of the dominance of English makes them dependant on the androcentric constructs of African customary practices operating to their detriment.

Methodology

The data for our article was obtained through a desktop evaluation of particular texts with the help of content analysis. According to leading scholars in the field, systematic content analysis can contribute to the creation of knowledge through creating a conceptual fit between research questions and its relationship to methodology. (Krippendorff, 2004). This research method was selected due to its potential and adaptability in the analysis associated with a social and legal examination.

The content analysis was carried out on of Section 9 of the 1996 Constitution, Section 26 of the Birth and Death Registrations Act 1992, the Children’s Act of 2005. The analysis,

in addition to that of the legislative Acts, also involved a systematic reading of the cases and journal articles related to naming practises to pinpoint the existence of meaningful and interesting pieces of content on the subject area. By labelling the relevant content of the legislation, precedents and articles, the researchers analysed patterns of content qualitatively to analyse meanings of content within texts (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Simple computational techniques like word frequencies, document lengths were used to automate the categorising and labelling of the documents. Online searches for cases and articles were limited from the year 2000 to 2024.

The actual content analysis of the texts aimed at identifying patterns and themes of behaviour, emotions and inherent prejudices in relation to naming practises in South Africa (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In the study the two researchers were the collaborators in the coding process. Each one of us was randomly responsible for 50% of the documentation which were later exchanged during the second cycle. After the first cycle of reading, the identification of additions in certain codes occurred. We looked for the existence of themes in both legal articles and cases associated directly and indirectly with the current legal practices and their roots.

Discussion

The daughter and naming practises

38

It appears that patriarchal entitlements of men as the superior subjects have filtered to all relationships that men hold, which creates discrimination and inequality for women in their various social positions as daughter, mother and wife. From very early on in a girl child's life, she is exposed to gender bias. In South Africa, the practice of patronymic naming for children is the default practice in the eye of the law. (Nduna, 2014).

Although the law allows for the procedure for breaking the tradition of patronymic naming it is exceptional. Girl children are taught to think and behave in an inferior manner and to understand that a boy is always their senior and the prospective head of the households first as their father and then later as a husband.

The South African law covers the aspect of name change in Section 26 of the Births and Registries Act. Women are free to make the decision on their own or in consultation with their partner when they are married. This means that the freedom of choice is available to women in South Africa, those who choose to get married as to whether they want to change their surnames or not. On the opposite side, there is a current trend in South Africa where women are opting to keep their maiden names for professional and other reasons.

The Department of Home Affairs states that the child's name must be registered by the parent who is responsible for the child. The situation continues according to Section 9 of the Births and Registries Act 1992, which allows for the child to be registered under the father's surname unless the child is illegitimate, in those circumstances the child is registered under the mother's surname. Section 28 of the Constitution protects the best interests of the child and entrusts the State to always safeguard and protect the rights of

the children. Therefore, it is concerning that Section 12 of the Children’s Act 2005 permits virginity testing of minors between the ages of 16 to 18 conditionally and allows marriages of minors provided that the child’s informed consent as well as the legal guardian’s is obtained. We maintain that these regulations are insufficient and superficially worded. The patriarchal and cultural context within which these practices occur means that children are still left legally unprotected. It is extremely difficult to expect children (the vulnerable members of our society) to stand up to their parents and community elders and to refuse to participate in “long standing cultural practices”.

Although the Act does prohibit female genital circumcision, the allowance of forced marriages and virginity testing encourages the violation and control of the female body and sexuality. Consequently, male superiority is endorsed within the cultural and legal frameworks. A forced marriage for a minor child has several consequences not only for her emotional and psychological development but also in terms of her own personhood. She is no longer under the protection of her father’s household or name if she ever was. A rational father would protect his daughter from *ukuthwala* as firstly, that is a father’s duty of care and secondly it is in terms of the constitutional mandate of the best interests of a child. This duty is overlooked, however, in certain instances families have supported the practice of *ukuthwala* as they stood to benefit financially by way of payment of the bride price: *lobola*. This becomes a serious hindrance to actualisation of gender equality.

In 2004 in the case of *Bhe and Others v Khayelistsha Magistrate and Others* (hereinafter referred to as the *Bhe* case) the practice of male primogeniture under the African customary law of succession. In the matter of *Bhe and Others*, the father of his deceased son was appointed as the representative and sole heir of his deceased son’s estate, as per African customary law. Mrs Bhe, the widow and the father of the deceased agreed that no marriage or customary union had taken place between Mrs Bhe and the deceased. Consequently, the two minor children, both extra-marital daughters, had no success in their attempt to qualify as heirs of their deceased father.

Male primogeniture was a customary principle of law that stated that only the eldest legitimate son could inherit the deceased’s estate, excluding other siblings. Tracing ancestral lineage through the paternal line has long been a fundamental foundation of African customary law to ensure male superiority. Section 23 of the Black Administration Act of 1927 barred female offspring from inheriting property and marginalised all females who followed the applicable customary law. However, male primogeniture was abolished as it discriminated against women and extramarital children. Further, the Reform of Customary Law of Succession Act 11 of 2009 abolished male primogeniture in South Africa, recognising equal inheritance rights for all surviving offspring and spouses. However, the norm continues to pose a barrier in some communities with a strong heritage in customary law and traditions. While the Constitution recognises customary law, it requires that such regulations uphold the Bill of Rights and does not discriminate against women.

The ruling in the *Bhe* case invalidated Section 23 of the Black Administration Act as well as section 1(4)(b) of the Intestate Succession Act. Ms Bhe and her daughters were not important regarding the question of ownership even though she was the partner of

the deceased and the mother of the deceased's two minor daughters. However, it was the deceased father who was authorised to act as sole heir for the deceased's estate by virtue of him being a male. The issue of lobola was also raised in this case and yet again is an acknowledgement that black females are reduced to commodities and their rights are derived in terms of what is granted to them by the male figures in their lives. It is apparent that there is no equality before the law and what the legislation does is provide justifiable grounds to perpetrate crimes and violate the rights of women and female children.

It is also important to note that the *Bhe* case highlights the naming conventions of women and the oppression that the title 'widow' signifies when Mrs Bhe no longer has the protection of her husband. As a widow and the two female children, they are not regarded as the rightful heirs to the property of their deceased husband and father, respectively. The title of widow and the status of female child serve to subjugate female subjects and reinforce established cultural norms of patriarchal oppression.

The female child is regarded as less valuable than the male child and in African custom the birth of a male child is celebrated more than that of a female child which has led to not only undervaluing one gender in favour of the other but promoting gender inequality. (Baloyi, Manala, 2019, p.1) In the African Tsonga custom there is a saying which states that to "*beget a woman is to beget a man*" which establishes and elevates the role of the male. (Baloyi, Manala, 2019, p.1) This quote means that a woman has no other purpose other than to give birth to a son. In addition, the saying highlights two points, it consoles the women birthing a female child that one day that female child will bear a son. (Baloyi, Manala, 2019, p.1) and secondly illustrates the unworthiness of a mother that births a daughter. Both notions serve the purpose of undermining the concept of motherhood and that of a daughter for no legitimate reason other than being female.

The wife and naming practises

Marriages alter a women's status and her identity. Women are positioned as commodities to be traded in by the dominant male figures in their lives and it is within this framework of patriarchy that the status of woman is undermined (Vengesayi,2018). Upon marriage, a wife undergoes a so-called acclimatisation process in which she is disorientated from her own culture to assimilate into her husband's culture. This may involve acquiring new thought patterns, language, or idealism from her husband's culture which is intrinsically linked to the payment of lobola. (Mawere, Mawere, 2010, p.231) The payment of *lobola* ensures her own self-worth and value within her husband's family as her role is to ensure the perpetuation of her husband's cultural traditions. (Mawere, Mawere, 2010, p.231)

The customary practice for the bride to alter her surname and assume her husband's surname takes place within this broader cultural context. The importance of the male surname becomes a means of domination and substance as opposed to the mother's surname, which is passed down from her own father. It is interesting to note that the view that a father's surname is appropriate for ancestral protection, is agreed upon in South Africa. The research carried out by Nduna in 2014 pinpointed the realities faced by young people who grew up without their biological fathers and losing their surnames.

His research contributed to an understanding of young people’s views regarding the relevance of biological of a paternal surname. His research based on in-depth interviews with 73 volunteers aged 14-39 in two South African provinces indicated that the pursuit for using a biologicals father’s surname was motivated by amongst other reasons seeking one’s father to access citizenship rights as a biological father’s surname was essential for registration for identity document, passport, marriage and death certificate. However, no agreement existed in the data regarding the importance and usefulness of using the father’s surname. In conclusion the article maintains that the father’s surname is important for some children who grew up without their fathers. (Nduna, 2014).

In the case of women, their identities are disrupted as they are obligated to make adjustments so that they transition as a wife and daughter-in-law. These roles become blurred as it appears that indigenous women do not just marry the man but the man’s family as well. The Nguni people, for example, refer to the wife as “makoti” (Resane,2023, p.2). The name makoti means “bride,” “newly married woman,” or “daughter-in-law,” and it is the term members of the husband’s family use to refer to her. Many people think that this phrase comes from the Afrikaans phrase “Maak ons tee” or the English phrase “Maker of Tea”. The irony is that this practise is presented as part of indigenous culture and is practised not only by men but by women too, in particular the senior women of the husband’s family.

If a woman gets married in South Africa currently, the following acts of legislation will regulate that marriage:

- The Marriage Act 25 of 161 – for the monogamous marriage of opposite-sex couples.
- The Recognition of Customary Marriages Act 120 of 1998 – for polygamous marriages of opposite-sex couples.
- The Civil Union Act 17 of 2006 – for monogamous partnerships for same-sex and opposite-sex couples
- The Births and Deaths Registration Act 51 of 1992 (BADRA)

In terms of section 26(1) of the Births and Deaths Registration Act 51 of 1992 (BADRA), a married woman has the option of adopting her husband’s surname or retaining her natal surname or a prior surname that she legally bore. It is significant that in a patriarchal society such as ours, married women now have a choice in terms of the law to take their husband’s surname or keep their birth surname or a prior surname legally held (Matladi, 2022, p.165). BADRA was amended in 2002 and allows women to merge their surnames with their husbands as double-barrelled surnames. Married women can choose to take their husband’s surname, keep their birth surname or legally bear a former surname, or merge their surnames as a double-barrelled surname. Matladi (2022, p.165) states that the married women do not have to apply to the Department of Home Affairs to retain or alter their surnames, but they would have to send written notification. However, several women have reported that the Department’s officials unilaterally changed their surnames despite married women informing them that they wished to retain surnames (Matladi, 2022, p.166). These actions are misogynistic and is contrary to the legal and constitutional frameworks. It oppresses and ignores the rights of women rendering them invisible. In terms of section 9(3) of the Constitution, it amounts to unfair discrimination based on gender, marital status, sex and dignity.

The objectification of women within the cultural framework that weakens the force of the legal reform is evident from the practices of *ukuthwala* and *lobola*. *Ukuthwala* deprives women of agency and autonomy over their own lives and bodies, reducing them to objects who are seized and married against their will. It regards women as commodities that can be exchanged, rather than equal human beings. As opposed to acknowledging women as equal partners in a marriage, *lobola* also reduces them to property that is purchased and sold. This commodification of women serves to reinforce the idea that their worth lies in their capacity to be exchanged, rather than in their inherent humanity (Vengesayi, 2018). These layers of oppression intersect on grounds of gender, political economy, and culture. Black women are at the centre of these systems of oppression, translating into gender and race specific harm (Mabasa, 2015). This is clear in *Jezile v S and Others (WCC) 127/2014* (hereafter called the *Jezile* case). The complainant, the wife of Jezile in this matter was raped and physically abused entrapped in a non-consensual marriage by the appellant, Jezile, the husband and the male members of his family (*Jezile*, 2013, p. 21). It was considered a case of *ukuthwala*, a culturally harmful practice that justifies the forced abduction of women or girls. The court held in this matter that Jezile be sentenced to ten years imprisonment for human trafficking and another twenty in respect of the three counts of rape. *Ukuthwala* violates the provisions of Section 8(d) of the Promotion of Equality and that of Prevention of Unfair Discrimination Act 2000 (hereafter called PEPUDA), which states that “any practice, including traditional, customary or religious practice, which impairs the dignity of women and undermines equality between women and men, including the undermining of the dignity and well-being of the girl child” (PEPUDA, 2000, p. 8). It is evident that the law is aligning itself with the constitutional values by recognising the rights of the wife to dignity and equality. Whilst this is a positive step, it is a small one in a country where the cultural practices are deeply enmeshed. conventional approaches to law and policy clearly demonstrates that the interests of black women and girls are not adequately served in addressing oppressive cultural practices (Mabasa, 2015, p. 30).

In South Africa, wives and mothers are constantly trying to find ways to earn an income to put food on the table for their family. Lack of education and high levels of poverty makes this extremely challenging. Their main source of income comes from farming, however even this is influenced by patriarchy and the law to overtly discriminates against women. The inadequacy of conventional approaches is evident in the discourse surrounding land ownership by black South African women, as the scarcity of land ownership among Black women is significantly lower than that of men. This underscores the inadequacy of policies regarding land distribution (Mubecua & Nojiyeza 2019.) Land expropriation was used to address racial and gender inequality in ownership of property however it has failed to address the challenges of ownership of land by Black women. (Mubecua & Nojiyeza, 2019). A possible reason for this is that it is an entrenched belief that men are the owners of property and in respect of the practice of primogeniture was entitled to land in favour of women. This situation of land ownership intersects with oppressive customary practices which is identified in *Bhe* case. Two Acts were canvassed in this case, the Intestate Succession Act 81 of 1987 (hereafter called the Intestate Act) and the Black Administration Act 38 of 1927 (hereafter the Act). Section 23 in the Act gives effect to the customary practice of succession which prescribes that estates must devolve in terms of

African customary law. This provision was repealed due to its unconstitutionality as the case highlighted many disparities in gender relations.

The mother and naming practises

It is observed that motherhood in South Africa is not an easy role, nor is it supported by laws, culture, or religion (Baloyi, Manala, 2019). Although customary law is recognised, it has historically discriminated against women and fails to adequately address the unique challenges faced by impoverished mothers.

The concept of motherhood and the way it develops is significantly influenced by the cultural context and the role of language in the transmission of cultural practices and ideas (Robinson, 2014, p.5). Further, motherhood in South Africa is based on extended family networks and the opportunity to engage in employment. Very often, young mothers in rural areas would leave their children in the care of the elderly grandparents (extended families) and venture into urban areas seeking employment. It is against this backdrop that the concept of “collective mothering” arose argues the World Health Organization (2020). This arrangement involves a shared responsibility by various females for all the young children in a community – this could be grandmothers, aunts, cousins etc. It is relevant to point out how this notion is in tune with the African philosophical term of *ubuntu*. The literal interpretation of the term is “I am, because we are” implying an interconnectedness and a sense of humanity which joins members of a community. Ubuntu can work positively for women. (Metz, 2011).

One can have a household of single motherhood or a two-parent household (Callaghan, et al, 2021). Due to the level of poverty faced in the country and for various other socio-economic reasons, the South African government pays a child support grant of R530.00 per month, per child to the primary caregiver. The caregiver which in most instances is the mother, would have to apply to government for the subsidy and have the requisite birth certificate as well as the South African identity book if applicable. Two out of every five households in the country have female headed households (Ndagurwa, *et al*, 2023); the house is headed up either by the grandmother or the aunt. However, the Children’s Act of 2005 favours the father and provides that a father obtains full parental responsibilities and rights in the child irrespective of whether he lives with the mother or not when the reality is that the majority of children are raised by their mothers and women are given no recognition for this. (South African Government, 2024)

The law’s disposition is reinforced by the fact that unmarried and single mothers in South Africa are exposed to social moralising (Bonthuys, 2018) Society judges’ mothers in this situation as being “unwanted” by a man, or worse yet, that she shamed her family and herself by bearing a child out of wedlock. It is obvious that there is no equality before the law and what the legislation does is provide justifiable grounds to perpetrate crimes and violate the rights of women and female children. The female child is regarded as less valuable than the male child and in African custom the birth of a male child is celebrated more than that of a female child which has led to not only undervaluing one gender in favour of the other but promoting gender inequality. (Baloyi, Manala, 2019, p. 1).

General Discussion

Paternal identity is important in African culture and despite their being no cultural significance or legitimacy in the practice of surnames it does hold value in cultural personal identity (Nduna, 2014). For children born out of wedlock this is extremely important as the paternal responsibility for assuming responsibility of the pregnancy is witnessed by the child assuming the father's surname and a verified claim to the child's paternal ancestry. A qualitative exploratory study in 2014, based on 73 interviews from amongst high school and tertiary institution students, employed and unemployed youths, many of African descent investigated the importance of a biological paternal surname (Nduna, 2014). The female subjects in the study voiced various concerns. One such concern dealt with them needing the father's surname to apply for a marriage or death certificate, passport or identity document. Many of the females mentioned the practice of "*Inhlawulo*" which is damages paid as compensation to the woman's family for her pregnancy out of wedlock by the biological father of the child yet to be born (Nduna, 2014). The view of the female portrayed as damaged reinforces the notion of her pecuniary value in society. This concept of "*Inhlawulo*" furthermore finds recognition in Section 21 of Children's Act dealing with the rights of unmarried fathers. The point to reiterate is that female children born from extra-marital relations are subjected to the two-fold effect of customary discriminatory practices. Firstly, children born out of wedlock are not recognised as legitimate heirs and secondly by virtue of being female you are excluded from inheriting. The stigma attached to the language of "an illegitimate female child" is far-reaching. It socialises the female child into beliefs of second-class citizenship by creating a hierarchy of unequal power (Vengesayi, 2018, p.1) and strips them of their constitutional right to equality and dignity.

44

In the *Bhe* case, the primogeniture system unfairly discriminated against two minor female heirs to their deceased father's wealth. The validity of heirs was also questioned, and customary law states that the husband and his family have full parental rights over children born from a marriage if the *lobola* agreement is met (Van Rensburg, 2001, p.5). According to this idea, children born from a customary union with outstanding *lobola* were illegitimate and belonged to the mother's family. To be labelled as "illegitimate" undermines female children's self-determination and reinforces customary practices' perception of unworthiness. In *Mthembu v Letsela* 1997 2 SA 936 (SCA) (the Mthembu case), the courts noted these forms of oppression by ruling that the daughter could not inherit because customary law excludes females and further that she was not a legitimate heir due to incomplete *lobola* payments. (*Mthembu v Letsela* 1997, p.8). The courts accepted the law as it was without challenging the issue of discrimination. Indeed, one can even go further to state that the courts used the language of the law to perpetuate discrimination. At no stage did the courts attempt to develop customary law to bring it in line with constitutional principles.

A key element in the *Jezi* case is that the complainant was powerless in respect of bodily integrity and dignity. Males decided her fate and bartered her like a commodity against a patriarchal background that infringed on her right to self-determination. Furthermore, these cultural practices are structurally invasive, manipulate women into being accomplices in their own oppression, and thereby perpetuate the cycle of violence and abuse. Notable is that some women accept and recognise their oppressors but not all oppressed people agree

that they are oppressed. (Mkhize and Vilakazi 2021, p.3). The *Jezile* case highlights the issues around sexual oppression and objectification of the female body which is normalised in cultural practices. This is evident from the appellants emphasis that his future wife had to be young, 16 years old in this instance and a virgin. (*Jezile v The State* 2016, p.5). In addition, what stands out as significant was despite resistance the complainant had to don traditional wear to partake in a customary ceremony that changed her status to a bride or “*makoti*” which normalised her as a possession of the appellant and a commodity through the payment of *lobola* thereafter. (*Jezile v The State* 2016). Naming conventions in this instance “*makoti*”, amounted to a system of sexist and patriarchal norms relied on to justify the conduct of the appellant and male family members. This is apparent in two instances, firstly when the complainant runs away to seek refuge and is sent back to the appellant by her own family members. Secondly, when the complainant’s mother who by virtue of being the natural parent had legal rights over protection and safe keeping of her minor daughter was voiceless in relation to the authority asserted by the male members of the family. (*Jezile v The State* 2016). “*Makoti*” therefore had the effect of reducing her to a possession of the male complainant and justified the actions of the male family members to violate her right to freedom, her right to choose and bodily integrity.

In terms of constitutional rights, it is not sufficient to merely acknowledge the existence of the rights. What is more important is that all citizens particularly females have the freedom to enjoy those rights. (Mkhize and Vilakazi, 2021, p.1) The enquiry delves into the lack of protection of those “freedoms” where it concerns women, including lesbian women’s right to bodily integrity where they are compelled to conform to the dictates of African customary law. Homosexuality is not recognised in African Customary Law as many prominent African leaders consider it “un-African” (Van der Westhuizen, 2019, p.44). It is also apparent that the Recognition of Customary Marriages Act makes no reference to “same-sex” marriages and the use of pronouns like “his” and “her” reinforces the fact that same-sex marriages are not contemplated in the Customary Marriage Act. The result is lesbian females are left in a very vulnerable position in accessing constitutional rights of equality, human dignity and freedom and security (Constitution, 1996, Chapter 2). Due to the contradictions found in customary law women are almost seen as undeserving of those rights (Mkhize and Vilakazi, 2021, p.2). This goes back to the point made earlier that policy and regulations have failed to address how naming conventions in African customary law has served as a tool to objectify and oppress women and female children.

Conclusion

The discriminatory naming practices that women encounter reflects the deep-seated gender inequalities that persists in contemporary South African society. Tradition, culture and the Law are used as vehicles to perpetuate stereotypes which serves to undermine the dignity and autonomy of women. However, jurisprudence, as seen in the *Bhe* and *Jezile* cases, indicates positive changes in the direction of gender equality, providing hope that the discriminatory norms are challenged and dismantled. While women continue to enforce their rights and demand substantive equality, the South African government must take concrete steps through legislation and public awareness campaigns to prohibit harmful

practices of patriarchy. The achievement of these objectives requires both the state and civil society to work together as naming practices are embedded within a deep-rooted cultural value system. The fight for the eradication of naming conventions is an integral part of the wider struggle for women's rights and empowerment in South Africa.

References

- Atanga, L., Ellece, S. E., Litosseliti, L. & Sunderland, J. (2012). Gender and language in sub-Saharan African contexts: Issues and challenges. *Gender and Language*, 6(1), pp. 1-20.
doi: 10.1558/genl.v6i1.1
- Archemour, A.A. (2018) "Naming of Children and meaning of names among the Akan of Ghana: Defining Identities?" SAJFS 1-14.
- Baloyi E.M. & Manala M.J. (2019) "Reflections on challenges of preferring the male child in an African Marriage – A practical theological observation" *Verbum Et Ecclesia*. 1-14
- Bekker J.C. & Buchner-Everleigh M (2017) "The legal character of ancillary customary marriages." *De Jure Law Journal*.80-96
- Bertucci, Mariono E, Haves, J.(2021). Constructivism Reconsidered: Past, Present and Future, VDOC <https://vdoc.pub/documents/constructivism-reconsidered-past-present-and-future-5midejgret40>.
- Bonthuys E. (2018) "A duty of Support for All South African Unmarried Intimate Partners Part 2: Developing Customary and Common Law and Circumventing the Volks Judgment" Vol 21 PER/PELJ 2-37 <http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/1727-3781/2018/v21i0a4411>
- Bryman, A & Bell, E.(2011). *Business Research methods*. (3rd ed). Cambridge: Oxford University Press. ISBN 9780199583409.OCLC 746155102.
- Callaghan, M.A., Watchiba D, Purkey, E, Colleen M., Davison, C.M, Aldersey, H.M. & Bartels, S.A. (2021). I Don't Know Where I Have to Knock for Support": A Mixed-Methods Study on Perceptions and Experiences of Single Mothers Raising Children in the Democratic Republic of Congo
- Chayinska M, Ukug O.M, Solak N, Kanik B & Cuvas B (2021) " Obstacles to the Birth Surname Retention Upon Marriage: How do Hostile Sexism and System Justification Predict Support for Marital Surname Change Among Women?" *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Craise, C & Scully, P. (2021). *Sara Baartman and the Hottentot Venus*. Princeton University Press.
- Houston, G, Kanyane, M & Davids YD (2022). *Paradise Lost : Race and Racism in Post-Apartheid South Africa*. Africa-Europe Group for Interdisciplinary Studies. Leiden: Brill, 2022. <https://0-unisaza-summon-serialssolutions-com.oasis.unisa.ac.za20Post-Apartheid%20South%20Africa>
- Krippendorff, K. (2004). *Content analysis: An Introduction to Its Methodology* (2nd ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Lafon, M. (2011). Linguistic diversity in South Africa: will a historically divisive factor become a hallmark for transformation? 2006. 142-164.
- Mabasa D. (2015) "Ukuthwala: Is it all culturally relative" *De Rebus* 28-30.
- Machaba, M.A. (2004) *Naming Identity and the African Renaissance in a South African context*. PHD, University of Natal.
- Maluleke, M.J. (2012) "Culture, Tradition Law and Gender Equality" *PELJ* 2-428
- Mathonsi N & Mpungose Z (2015) "Perceived Gender Inequality Reflected in Zulu Proverbs: A Feminist Approach 30-42
- Madubuike. I. (1975). "Decolonization of African Names." *Presence Africaine Editions* 39-49

- Matladi, O. (2022). What Is in Surname? An Enquiry into the Unauthorised Name Changes of Married Women. *Pretoria Student Law Review*, 16, 164-184.
- Mawere M & Mawere A M, (2010) “The changing philosophy of African marriage: The relevance of the Shona customary marriage practice of Kukumbira” *Journal of African Studies and Development* Vol. 2(9), pp. 224-233 <http://www.academicjournals.org/JASD>
- Metz, T. (2011). *Ubuntu* as a moral theory and human rights in South Africa. *African Human Rights Journal*. 532-539.
- Mkhize, G & Vilakazi, F. (2021) Rethinking Gender and Conduits of Control: A feminist review.
- Mubecua M. A. & Nojiyeza S (2019) Land Expropriation without Compensation: The Challenges of Black South African Women in Land Ownership DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31920/2050-4284/2019/8n3a1>
- Mwambene, L. & Sloth-Nielsson, J. (2011). Benign accommodation? *Ukuthwala*, ‘forced marriage’ and the South African Children’s Act. *African Human Rights Law Journal*. 1-22.
- Ndagurwa, P., Naidoo, L. & Miles-Timotheus, S. (2023). The distribution of male-headed and female-headed households in Gauteng. *Map of the Month*. Gauteng City-Region Observatory. March 2023.
- Ndinda, C & Ndlovu, TP. (2022). The Intersectionality of Gender, Race and Class in the Transformation of the Workplace on Post-apartheid South Africa, Chapter 14 in: *Paradise Lost: Race and Racism in Post-apartheid South Africa*, 98-1222. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004515949_005.
- Nduna, M. (2014) “Growing up without a father and a Pursuit for the *Right* Surname.” *The Open Family Studies Journal*. 31-38.
- Neuendorf, K. (2016). *The Content Analysis Guidebook*. Sage.
- Robinson, G. S. (2014) “Attitudes to motherhood and working mothers in South Africa: Insights from quantitative attitudinal data” University of KwaZulu-Natal Masters https://www.embrace.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Robinson_2014_Attitudes-to-Motherhood-and-Working-Mothers.pdf accessed 30/09/2024
- Resane, K.T. (2023) *A makoti* in a Patriarchal Society: Culture, Christianity, and Constitution in Collision? *Scriptura* vol.122 n.1 Stellenbosch 2023. <https://dx.doi.org/10.7833/122-1-2112>.
- RSA History Online 2024 History Women’s Struggle South Africa. <https://sahistory.org.za/article/history-womens-struggle-south-africa>
- Tshipani, RA. Challenges faced by females occupying leadership position at selected South African Higher Education Institutions, South Africa <https://univendspace.univen.ac.za/items/e602504a-82cf-4651-9e68-058f39ebf7c8>.
- Van der Westhuizen CM (2019) “The (non)-recognition of same-sex marriage in the Recognition of Customary Marriages Act 120 of 1998.” *Journal of Juridical Science*. 44-67
- Van Rensburg A.M. (2001) “Mthembu v Letsela: The Non-Decision” 1-16 SLTSA paper
- Vengesayi P (2018) “Lobola (Bride Price) Culture and the Equality of Women in Zimbabwe” *Pretoria Student Law Review* 112-135.
- Wa Thiong’o, N. (1993). *Moving the Center: The Struggle for Cultural Freedoms*. James Currey Limited. London.
- White, M.D, & Marsh, E.E. (2006). Content Analysis: A Flexible Methodology. *Library Trends* 55(1), 22-45. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/lib.2006.0053>.

Case Law

- Bhe and Others v Khayelistsha Magistrate and Others (CCT 49/03) [2004] ZACC 17;2005 (1) SA 580 (CC)
- Jezile v S and Others (WCC) 127/2014 [2015]
- Mthembu v Letsela 1997 2 SA 936 (SCA)

Legislation

1996 Constitution of the Republic of South Africa No.108 of 1996

The Birth and Death Registrations Act 51 of 1992

The Children's Act 38 of 2005

The Civil Union Act 17 of 2006

Websites

Child Support Grant, <https://www.gov.za/services/child-care-social-benefits/child-support-grant> accessed 30/09/2024

People of South Africa, <https://www.gov.za/about-sa/south-africas-people> accessed 30/09/2024